

Deliverable: 2.4: Specifications of I- NERGY - AI4EU Cross-fertilisation, Synergies and Alignment (first version)

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Executive Summary

AI4EU is a European AI-on-demand platform that facilitates knowledge transfer and provides basic guidelines. This platform also offers reusable resources for both research and business. The resources are shared with the community and are readily available for reuse and integration into new innovative services and products. Therefore, this Platform offers a unique opportunity for a common platform and reusable AI components that follow defined standards. Consequently, new products and services can use many of the existing services in the AI4EU platform. Therefore, it helps innovation of the new products/services quickly and promptly. In this context, this deliverable presents the work done to define the Specifications of I-ENERGY - AI4EU Cross-Fertilisation, Synergies & Alignment.

The objective of the deliverable is twofold: first, it identifies existing services in the AI4EU platform that are in line with the usage scenarios of I-ENERGY to encourage the re-use and strengthening of the services. Secondly, it provides the specification and guidelines for integrating new extensions to the AI4EU platform. Specifically, it provides guidelines for integrating I-ENERGY AI-on-demand Energy Services as defined in T2.1(I-ENERGY Technology Requirements & User Stories) into the AI4EU functionalities. The deliverable is part of the WP2 task T2.4: Specifications of I-ENERGY - AI4EU Cross-Fertilisation, Synergies & Alignment. The result of the work provides: (i) a collection of a commonly agreed set of guidelines for integrating envisaged services of I-ENERGY into the AI4EU platform. (ii) Analysis of the existing services and resources of AI4EU in the context of envisaged I-ENERGY services.

Another important aspect is the infrastructure for the execution of envisaged I-ENERGY services. The AI4EU platform provide a set of services including an AI catalogue for sharing AI knowledge and resources as well as a design studio to create pipelines for AI services (AI4EU experiments platform). This deliverable shed light on the deployment of the services on the local infrastructure and provides the necessary guidelines and the procedure for the local deployment of the services. Lastly this deliverable presents a preliminary analysis of the existing components/services/guidelines in the I-ENERGY project in view of alignment with the AI4EU offerings.

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Glossary

Term	Definition	Term	Definition	Term	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence	GUI	Graphical User Interface	ML	Machine Learning
AEM	AI4EU Experiments Management	GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation	NLP	Natural Language Processing
EU	European Union	gRPC	Google Remote Procedure Call	OS	Operating System
CV	Computer Vision	IoT	Internet of Things	PoC	Proof of Concept
CM	Collaborative Management	IAM	Identity and Access Management	RPC	Remote Procedure Call
DL	Deep Learning	LSTM	Long short-term memory	XML	Extensible Markup Language

1 Introduction

This deliverable relates to Task 2.4 - Specifications of I-ENERGY - AI4EU Cross-fertilisation, Synergies and Alignment. The focus of this first version of the deliverable is to present an analysis of the existing EU project's AI on-demand (AI4EU) platform and provide guidelines for developing and deploying AI components (models, selected set of data, AI pipelines, etc.) for foreseen I-ENERGY services. Moreover, this deliverable also presents the strategic cross-fertilisation and alignment efforts between I-ENERGY and AI4EU projects.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is changing every field of life, and the energy sector is no different from it. Currently, deep learning is thriving, and it is changing the shape of every industry [1]. However, deep learning methods need a lot of data to train [1]. Fortunately, there is a lot of data available in the energy sector. The sources of this data include smart grid sensors, open data sources and simulators. Therefore, the effective use of AI in the energy sector can significantly impact the energy sector value chain. The I-ENERGY project aims to bridge the gap between the advances in AI and the current practices in the energy sector. The idea is to provide coordinated set AI services that are modular and highly reusable. Since the Deliverable D2.1 [2] already identified the I-ENERGY services and Deliverable 2.2 [3] specified the ethical guidelines for AI components, this deliverable D2.4 (Specifications of I-ENERGY - AI4EU Cross-fertilisation, Synergies and Alignment) effectively aligns I-ENERGY with AI4EU (Europe's one-stop AI shop).

The alignments and synergies have been considered in many dimensions. However, the first and the foremost is the set of guidelines that one can follow to develop the services that are highly reusable and can readily be integrated into the AI4EU platform for immediate use in the AI pipelines. The development of such services will help the adaptation of AI services in the energy sector. Therefore, the guidelines include onboarding, metadata specification along with GDPR Compliance and Trustworthy AI. Secondly, a brief and precise description of the AI4EU components follows. That will help the users to get to know the platform better. Since the deliverable is concerned with cross-fertilisation and synergies between AI4EU and I-ENERGY, another parallel dimension is the participation in open calls, development of common ontologies and dissemination. The organisation of this section is as follows: Section 1.1 concisely states the purpose of the document, and Section 1.2 elaborates the structure of the document. Finally, Section 1.3 explains the relation of this deliverable with the other tasks of the I-ENERGY project.

1.1 Purpose

This deliverable in correspondence with Task 2.4 aims to:

- provide an overview of the AI4EU platform;
- provide the specifications defined by the AI4EU platform for integrating new extensions to it;
- provide an overview of the current onboarding and deployment strategies of various components on the AI4EU platform;
- analyse how to integrate I-ENERGY AI-on-demand Energy Services [2] (from D2.1) into the AI4EU functionalities;

- provide synergies and existing material already produced by the AI4EU project that can contribute or be reused by the services prescribed by I-ENERGY.

In this manner, it will be a guideline for deploying the AI-based INERGY components and services. Furthermore, it serves as a guideline for developing the new components and services such that they are compliant with the AI4EU platform and reusable. Similarly, identifying the existing I-ENERGY relevant AI4EU services boosts the current development efforts of I-ENERGY services and components by promoting reusability.

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is organised in four main sections as described below:

- Section 1 provides the introduction regarding the purpose, scope, structure, and relation to the project's other tasks.
- Since AI4EU is our focus for developing and deploying the I-ENERGY components and services, in Section 2, the AI4EU platform and its related components are discussed. The components include
 - AI4EU Catalogue (for uploading models, datasets, etc.)
 - AI4EU Experiments (Building pipelines)
 - AI4EU Marketplace (facilitating users to find and reuse components)
 - AI4EU Community tools (News, Events).

This section also briefly discusses the related technologies one needs to know to understand the components mentioned above, specifically AI4EU Experiments.

- In Section 3, first, the overall plan for contribution to the different components of AI4EU is discussed. This section further discusses the strategic alignment and cross-fertilisation strategies between I-ENERGY and AI4EU projects. Furthermore, the I-ENERGY use cases related to the existing deployed resources and pipelines at the AI4EU platform are discussed. To validate the usefulness, this section also incorporates the feedback from project partners for the usefulness of the existing AI4EU resource and I-ENERGY use cases. Finally, this section discusses the template and exemplifies the synergy based on one use case. A detailed description is provided in Appendix 2 (section 7) that discusses all the 15 use cases within the project's scope.
- Section 4 describes how the different types of components (AI models, Data-brokers, etc.) are uploaded and integrated within the framework of AI4EU. Currently, the deployment facility is not available at the AI4EU platform. Therefore, this section also discusses how to deploy a pipeline of AI4EU locally.

The document is concluded in section 5 with an outlook of the future directions.

1.3 Relations to I-ENERGY Environments

The analysis performed in Task 2.4 (Specifications of I-ENERGY - AI4EU Cross-fertilisation, Synergies and Alignment) provides the basic building blocks in terms of guidelines for creating, integrating, and deploying the components and service of I-ENERGY for the AI4EU platform. The outcomes of this task are closely related to the following internal tasks of the project

- Task 2.1 AI-on-demand Energy Services Specifications since this task describes all the usage scenarios and requirements of the I-ENERGY project.
- Task 2.2 AI-related Ethical Guidelines and Recommendations since this task describes all the necessary guidelines for AI ethics and GDPR guidelines that are compulsory for developing AI components.
- Task 3.3 Incremental, Distributed & Self-learning Model Definition and Training since this task is related to AI models' training.
- Task 3.4 Cross-stakeholder Transfer Learning since this task is related to model training with transfer learning.
- Task 3.5 Model Evaluation and Serving Framework since this task is related to the serving of AI models.
- Task 4.2. Digital Twins for Energy Consumers Clustering/Segmentation for Electrical and Thermal Communities since this task will develop and train AI models (clustering and segmentation).
- Task 4.4. AI-based Big Data & ML for Finer Grained Energy and Flexibility Forecasting since this task also develops AI-based models (forecasting).
- Task 4.5 I-ENERGY Marketplace regarding I-ENERGY's alignment with the the AI4EU platform.
- Task 4.6. Reinforce the service layer of the AI4EU platform since this task deals with the ways that the AI4EU service layer will be enforced (AI4EU Catalogue and Experiments).

2 AI4EU Platform

The AI4EU project is a European Union's initiative for the development of the European AI Ecosystem. The project started in 2019 with the involvement of 70 partners from 21 different countries. The primary purpose of the project is to unify the European AI Community. In addition, the project aims to create Europe's leading AI platform for On-Demand AI services.

The underlying fundamental part of the AI4EU project is the AI4EU platform developed to mobilize the whole AI community in Europe¹. Furthermore, the goal of the AI4EU platform is to create a leading platform under which all the members of the European AI community can collaborate and engage with each other. Thus, the AI4EU platform combines the AI stakeholders and AI resources together on a single devoted platform to accelerate the production of AI-based research, products, and solutions.

The AI-on-demand platform is open to all user communities, such as the I-ENERGY project. Therefore, not only one can utilise the current resources (e.g., datasets, algorithms, tools, and models) but also upload their resources. As the AI4EU project is ending this year, the AI-on-demand platform's main contents include the AI4EU experiments platform, AI4EU community, and AI Catalog. Since this platform will serve as a single place to acquire AI knowledge, services, software, and experts, therefore, while designing the AI4EU platform following design principles [4] were considered:

- Service-oriented and Web Platform: The AI4EU platform is designed to be accessed from a web browser without installing any local machine dependency.
- Multi-disciplinary and cross-sector: AI4EU provides AI-based solutions for a varied range of machine learning problems. In contrast to existing research communities, AI4EU offers immediate access to AI technologies in numerous fields.
- Scalable and Interoperable: The AI4EU Platform is entirely scalable and interoperable among different programming languages, data sources, and third-party platforms.
- Curated Data Access: AI4EU includes various EU projects incorporating Big Data communities. Moreover, it will further be supported with more data from various affiliated partners.
- Collaborative, Social, and Confidential: The AI4EU Platform enables to build online teams sharing pipelines, modules, and experiments directed towards similar goals.

¹ <https://www.ai4europe.eu/>

Figure 1 Stakeholders and service requirement in a nutshell [4]

Figure 1 illustrates the stakeholders and the service level requirements for the AI4EU platform. The platform provides various services to its stakeholders, including AI Datasets, Algorithms, AI-based applications, training/education material, etc. Furthermore, the platform provides the environment in which European AI members can exchange information with the AI experts and apply for financial fundings to develop a sustainable business model. The AI4EU platform can have several stakeholders, including large companies to mature and immature start-ups requiring AI-based services.

Furthermore, the stakeholders can be researchers trying to develop state-of-the-art methods in different domains or developers working on the application side. In addition, the stakeholders can be teachers or educators that require AI-based modules to illustrate the AI concepts. At last, the stakeholders can be the public society in which anyone who wants to experiment can use this platform.

This section first outlines the architectural overview of the AI4EU platform (Section 2.1) followed by fundamental components of the AI4EU platform, such as AI Catalogue (Section 2.2), AI4EU Experiments (Section 2.3), Market place (Section 2.4), AI Community (Section 2.5). All these essential components of the AI4EU platform are highlighted in Figure 1. The AI Resource Catalogue components of the AI4EU platform allow users to upload resources such as Dataset, Executables, AI Models, Docker containers, Jupyter Notebooks As a Service or Library under various Technical and Business categories. The AI4EU Experiments component empowers users to develop their customised pipelines by designing them through a simple drag and drop activity on the graphical user interface editor called design studio (based on Acumos software). Another platform provided by the AI4EU project is the AI4EU Marketplace that serves as an additional channel that enables external partners, stakeholders, or other users to access data services, optimisation modules, AI models, and standalone applications packaged in a dockerised container.

Furthermore, the AI4EU Community Tools platform allows an easy-to-navigate overview of the community and keeps updating and posting about recent developments. Finally, the News and Event component of AI4EU facilitates the users to be informed about the latest advancements in different tools and technologies. It also gives users the option to filter the news based on relevance.

2.1 Architecture Overview

All the modules of the AI4EU platform are organised in one of the three layers [4]. The following subsections provide a brief description of these layers.

2.1.1 End-User Layer:

This layer targets the consumer dimension of the platform. It incorporates web applications and the services that are dedicated to the end-user of the AI4EU platform. The end-user layer of the AI4EU platform comprises of four components:

- Collaborative Management (CM): This component enables the end-users to have a dedicated “social network” that allows users to collaborate and exchange information. Furthermore, the CM includes other essential components of the AI4EU platform, such as the AI4EU Resource Catalogue consisting of datasets, models, code, containers, notebooks, etc.
- AI4EU Experiments Management (AEM): The AI4EU architecture facilitates multiple instances of AEM components. However, at the moment, the development operates on a single instance. This instance aims to integrate Acumos, which is an open-source technology. The AI4EU architecture provisions the ability to integrate other technologies. The interoperability of AI4EU and an AEM technology requires a two ways conversion of the AEM component catalogue to/from the CM component catalogue.
- Identity and Access Management (IAM): This component centralises the authentication and authorization system to operate on a single sign-on. OAuth2² and WS02³ technologies are used to implement this tool.
- Search: By employing the Qwant technology⁴ for web search., this component can look for information within the scope of web, CM data, and AEM data. Moreover, it provides a front end that can handle entire scope queries by delegating sub queries to each sub-component.

2.1.2 Orchestration Layer

The orchestration layer tackles the orchestration of the applications and services of the end-user layer. Furthermore, the orchestration layer controls the serviceability requirements of the platform from the end-user layer level. All the DevOps related technologies such as Docker and Kubernetes come under the orchestration layer. Moreover, this layer incorporates applications devoted to the developers and operators of the AI4EU platform and is less known among the end-users. Some of the involved applications are as follows:

- Drone.io⁵ + Gitea⁶: a continuous integration service.
- Rancher⁷: Rancher is an open-source container management platform. It includes,

² <https://oauth.net/2/>

³ <https://wso2.com/>

⁴ <https://about.qwant.com/en/>

⁵ <https://www.drone.io/>

⁶ <https://gitea.io/>

amongst others, a full Kubernetes distribution.

- Prometheus⁸: monitoring software that has been selected for the AI4EU platform

2.1.3 Infrastructure Layer

The infrastructure layer facilitates by supplying the resources such as RAM, CPU, storage, network, and GPUs to the platform orchestrator. Moreover, this layer incorporates the security-related constraints that ensure availability, integrity, confidentiality, and traceability. Furthermore, this layer provides the comfortable migration from one infrastructure to another, especially from the development infrastructure to the production infrastructure.

2.2 AI4EU Resource Catalogue

The main module of the AI4EU platform is Resource Catalogue⁹, where users can upload resources such as Dataset, Executable, AI Model, Docker container, Jupyter Notebook, etc. These resources are added under various Technical and Business categories. Business categories include the application area of AI (Artificial Intelligence), e.g., AI for Agriculture, AI for Traffic Management, etc. The purpose of Business categories is to provide and measure the direct impact of AI on human lives. On the other hand, the technical category consists of the main branches of AI, e.g., Computer Vision (CV), Natural Language Processing (NLP), Deep Learning (DL), etc. Most of the advancements in AI-based algorithms and models are recorded under this category. It also allows users to add new models under specific application areas, and other users can benefit from the latest models. Figure 2 depicts the layout of the resource catalogue platform of AI4EU.

⁷ <https://rancher.com/>

⁸ <https://prometheus.io/>

⁹ <https://www.ai4europe.eu/research/ai-catalog>

Figure 2 Screenshot outlining the Resource catalogue platform of AI4EU.

2.3 AI4EU Experiments

The AI4EU Experiment¹⁰ is an essential platform by AI4EU that provides a technical environment to interact, design and build AI pipelines. AI pipeline is a process in which several AI resources are interconnected to create an autonomous AI module. This AI module can be integrated with the services or applications. The AI4EU Experiments empower users to build these autonomous pipelines through a simple drag-and-drop activity on the GUI editor. This GUI editor is known as the Design Studio.

The Design Studio incorporates several features such as data transformation tools, machine learning models, and data sources. The machine learning models can be integrated with data

¹⁰ <https://acumos-int-fhg.ai4eu.eu/#/home>

source tools and data transformation tools without writing a single line of code for creating the AI modules. The AI4EU Experiments [4] work on the instance of Acumos and allow the users to upload machine learning models. Furthermore, these models can be shared with other all or restricted members of the AI community.

AI4EU Experiments was initialised as a fork of Acumos¹¹ and runs on its own instance. Acumos is an open-source Linux Foundation¹² AI project that implements a database catalogue and visual composer. It is a microservice-based architecture running on the Kubernetes cluster. AI4EU Experiments allows users to upload machine learning models. These models can be shared with other (all or restricted) members within the AI4EU community.

Moreover, AI4EU Experiments empowers users to develop their customised pipelines through simple drag and drop operations on a GUI editor called Design Studio. Some of the Design Studio features include data transformation tools, machine learning models, and data sources utilised to create AI-based solutions. Figure 3 depicts the outlook of the AI4EU Experiments.

Figure 3 Screenshot explaining the outlook of AI4EU Experiments.

The main component of AI4EU Experiments is Acu-Compose which is a subcomponent of Acumos (Design Studio). This is an environment for designing AI pipelines. It is a microservice-based architecture running on the Kubernetes cluster.

¹¹ <https://www.acumos.org/>

¹² <https://www.linuxfoundation.org/>

2.3.1 Prerequisite Concepts and Technologies for AI4EU Experiments

2.3.1.1 Docker

Docker¹³ is an open-source tool that provides the facility to execute the deployment process of various programs into the containers by abstracting the whole program with an additional layer in the Operating System (OS)-level virtualisation on Linux. The containers present in docker enable the configuration of the host OS. Moreover, they replicate virtual machines' same level of isolation, consuming a fraction of the computing power-on-demand.

2.3.1.2 Kubernetes

The next module needed for the deployment is Kubernetes¹⁴, an open-source system built on the Google Platform. We have just discussed Docker containers in section 2.3.1.1 above. For managing those Docker containers, a Kubernetes cluster is required. Kubernetes helps to manage containerised applications in various types of physical, virtual, and cloud environments. Figure 4 exhibits the architecture of Kubernetes along with its essential components. There are four basic components to get familiarised with Kubernetes:

2.3.1.2.1 *Cluster:*

A cluster is a series of host servers that adds all the available computing resources, including ram, CPU, hard drives, and other devices, into a pool that can be shared and used.

2.3.1.2.2 *Master:*

In the cluster, one node controls the panel of Kubernetes, which is called the Master node. It makes all the decisions for cluster along with scheduling jobs.

2.3.1.2.3 *Node:*

Node is a single resource on which a job can be run, and it can be a physical or a virtual machine. The node should be able to execute minikube¹⁵, kubelet¹⁶, and kube-proxy¹⁷, which are the components of the cluster.

2.3.1.2.4 *Namespace:*

A namespace is a logical environment that defines the scoping access for a cluster.

¹³ <https://www.docker.com/>

¹⁴ <https://kubernetes.io/>

¹⁵ <https://minikube.sigs.k8s.io/docs/>

¹⁶ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/reference/command-line-tools-reference/kubelet/>

¹⁷ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/reference/command-line-tools-reference/kube-proxy/>

Figure 4 Visual illustration of Kubernetes architecture ¹⁸

2.3.1.3 gRPC

gRPC¹⁹ is a current publicly accessible high-performance Remote Procedure Call (RPC) framework executable on any environment. It allows the services to conveniently connect with other modules from various data centres by leveraging load balancing, tracing, health checking, and authentication. It is also used in distributed computing to integrate mobile and web applications to back-end servers.

2.3.2 Pipeline Creation

In Acumos, a pipeline can be simply created by using the drag and drop feature of the Design Studio. Since the visual editor knows the method signatures defined using protobuf²⁰, which helps the user to connect the proper interfaces by matching the method signatures. The public interface of the model needs to be described as a protobuf definition which means that the service methods that a model offers to the rest of the pipeline should be defined in a relevant protobuf definition file (Section 4.2).

¹⁸ <https://www.guru99.com/kubernetes-tutorial.html>

¹⁹ <https://grpc.io/>

²⁰ <https://developers.google.com/protocol-buffers>

2.3.3 Validation and Deployment of the Pipeline

It is essential to mention that AI4EU Experiments is not an execution environment but rather a design environment. Therefore, a Kubernetes cluster needs to be provided by the user as an execution environment to deploy the created pipeline. AI4EU Experiments requires that the onboarded modules are dockerised to ensure that the modules are reusable and interoperable. Furthermore, the public interface of the model needs to be described as a protobuf definition which means that the service methods that a model offers to the rest of the pipeline should be defined in a relevant protobuf definition file. The communication is based on gRPC due to its efficient and standardised communication. Furthermore, by using the gRPC communication, code can be regenerated in many programming languages, which makes the automatic generation of artifacts possible.

2.3.4 Orchestrator

Once the pipeline is validated by ensuring the constraints of interoperability and reusability, the pipeline is deployed through Kubernetes Deployer and managed by the Orchestrator. The Orchestrator provides the automation by deploying, monitoring, tracking, and ensuring the safety of the AI pipelines. In general, the Orchestrator offers the following functionalities:

- Automation of the processes, regardless of the installed hardware or frameworks.
- Regularise best methods to make the operation more efficient.
- Generic interfaces that can connect methods from different sources without using scripting and programming languages.

Mainly, there are three kinds of orchestrators:

1. Serial Orchestrator
2. Parallel Orchestrator
3. Stream Orchestrator

2.3.4.1 The current state of AI4EU Orchestrator

It is crucial to mention that serial orchestrator is used in local deployment at the moment. However, in the future, Parallel and Stream Orchestrators may become available from the AI4EU platform. The General Serial Orchestrator is operated on the client-server framework of the gRPC. The client script is a part of the package solution, which will be deployed as a location solution, whereas the Kubernetes script builds the deployment for the orchestrator server. Furthermore, AI4EU is currently not providing compute resources for the deployment of the solutions. Ultimately, it is required to download the solution from AI4EU and deploy it locally, where the serial orchestration will be used as per the current state of the AI4EU platform.

2.4 AI4EU Marketplace

AI4EU Marketplace²¹ is a component of the AI4EU platform that serves as an additional channel that enables external partners, stakeholders, or other users to access different services. These

²¹ <https://acumos-int-fhg.ai4eu.eu/index.html#/marketPlace#marketplaceTemplate>

services include data services, optimisation modules, AI models, and standalone applications packaged in Docker containers. Figure 5 provides an overview of the AI4EU Experiments Marketplace.

Figure 5 Screenshot outlining the Marketplace platform of AI4EU Experiments.

2.5 AI4EU Community Tools

AI4EU also provides the AI4EU Community²² platform, where interested individuals and organisations across the whole EU can participate and utilise resources to create AI-based solutions. The AI4EU Community platform provides an easy-to-navigate overview of the community and keeps updating and posting about recent developments. Therefore, users are always informed on the current progress and have the opportunity to contribute and interact with the experts. Figure 6 presents the overview of the AI4EU Community.

²² <https://www.ai4europe.eu/ai-community>

Figure 6 Screenshot outlining the Community platform of AI4EU.

2.5.1 AI4EU News and Events

The news about the latest additions to catalogues, such as Models, Databases, etc., are provided in this segment of the AI4EU platform. Upcoming events can also be seen in this section, along with community news. This allows users to be informed about all the latest advancements in different tools and technologies. It also gives users the option to filter the news based on relevance. Figure 7 illustrates the main webpage of AI4EU News and Events²³.

²³ <https://www.ai4europe.eu/news-and-events>

Figure 7 Screenshot outlining the News and Events platform of AI4EU.

2.5.2 WebCafés

The AI4EU WebCafés²⁴ allow users to engage virtually in online sessions with experts from various AI domains. Moreover, the user can look up the list of upcoming Web Cafes and find a list of past Web Cafes related to AI. Figure 8 depicts the screenshot of the AI4EU WebCafés webpage.

²⁴ <https://www.ai4europe.eu/news-and-events/events/webcafes>

Figure 8 Screenshot of AI4EU Web Cafes

3 AI4EU Cross-Fertilisation, Synergies, and Alignment Specifications

This section discusses the alignment of I-ENERGY and AI4EU. Specifically, Section 3.1 first discusses the actual and envisaged contribution of I-ENERGY to the AI4EU platform. While Section 3.1 provides the preview, Section 3.2 digs deeper into the strategic cross-fertilisation between the I-ENERGY and AI4EU projects. Therefore, it explains the contributions in terms of open calls, development of common ontologies in perspective of I-ENERGY for highly interoperable components, essential dissemination points, and future plans. Finally, Section 3.3 discusses how the I-ENERGY use cases can be related to the existing services, pipelines, and tutorials available at the AI4EU platform. It also incorporates the feedback from I-ENERGY partners for the usefulness of the existing AI4EU services and I-ENERGY use cases. Furthermore, it describes the templates for the alignment of AI components of I-ENERGY and AI4EU.

3.1 AI-on-demand I-ENERGY Services Specifications

This section discusses the envisaged specifications for onboarding the I-ENERGY components on the AI4EU platform. The I-ENERGY project is expected to develop Data and AI services. Figure 9 illustrates the overall planning of the I-ENERGY project’s service onboarding and the strategies of cross-fertilisation and synergies with the AI4EU project.

Figure 9: Summary of services planning for AI4EU

I-ENERGY project anticipates the development of different Data and AI services during the course of the project. While data remains primarily private, it is proposed to integrate the AI services into the AI4EU platform. Consequently, it can be discovered by the AI4EU community through tools like AI4EU Experiments / Marketplace or AI4EU AI Catalog.

While Figure 9 depicts the complete umbrella of AI4EU components and the interaction, an even more simplified view of this process is shown in Figure 10. A submodule is created and onboarded at the AI4EU platform using the AI4EU Experiments. Once the submodule review is successful and it becomes available at the AI4EU platform, it can be used in any AI pipeline. Furthermore, It can be deployed using local resources. Section 4 provides further details concerning deployment concepts.

Figure 10: Block diagram for onboarding components on AI4EU platform

Furthermore, Figure 9 depicts the cross-fertilisation and alignment strategies that contribute mainly to the AI4EU Community. It includes participation in AI discussion groups, publishing I-ENERGY specific news and events, participation in the AI Web Café and Webinars. Section 3.2 provides more details about the cross-fertilisation and alignment strategies.

3.2 Strategic Cross-Fertilisation Between I-ENERGY and AI4EU

3.2.1 Open Calls

I-ENERGY will launch two Open Calls to select 25 bottom-up projects (SMEs/start-ups), distributing up to 2 million euros among them. The selection process will prioritise projects maximising the impact of the platform and demonstrating the benefit of AI in products, processes, or services. The selected projects should also cover a wide spread of application to demonstrate the versatility and scalability of the platform offers. This is aligned with the AI4EU objective of funding SMEs and start-ups benefitting from AI resources available on the platform to solve AI challenges and promote new solutions with AI.

An Open Distributed Model is established among all ICT48 and ICT49 projects, including I-ENERGY, whereby all open calls are published on the AI4EU platform and their results, specifically in the AI4EU Catalogue located at AI4EU Experiments²⁵.

Additionally, cross dissemination of all Open Calls and selected success stories of beneficiaries will be established, including sharing other potential common elements like, for example, Open Call Document Packages or Ethics Evaluation approaches.

3.2.2 Dissemination

The I-ENERGY project, along with the rest of ICT-49 projects (including AI4Copernicus, AIPlan4EU, BonsAPPs, DIH4AI and StairwAI), have already established a communication channel and regular meetings schedule regarding synergies for the dissemination activities with AI4EU. The scope of these meetings is to bring together ICT-49 Projects, define a common dissemination plan, explore potential synergies for both communication and dissemination activities and secure the sustainability of the AI4EU Platform. In that direction, common actions have already been agreed with the ICT-49 projects:

- a) Introductory posts of all ICT-49 projects will be published on the AI4EU social media accounts, including common ICT-49 hashtags (e.g., #ICT49, #AI4EU, #AI). The following

²⁵ <https://acumos-int-fhg.ai4eu.eu/#!/marketPlace#marketplaceTemplate>

- steps are for each ICT-49 project to use the common hashtags on their posts to create a common logo (more probably to add the AIEU logo to the existing logos).
- b) A dedicated page on the project websites referring to ICT-49 Projects / AI4EU. At the same time, AI4EU plans to provide shared space on the AI4Europe platform for ICT 49 projects.
 - c) Newsletters of different partners can be used for the dissemination of all ICT49 projects and the ICT49 working group, as well.
 - d) Identify events for dissemination of Open Calls – SMEs
 - e) The organisation of common events or promotion of individual events organised by members
 - f) The organisation of AI4EU Web Cafes and webinars from the projects
 - g) Common development of a promo video where a representative from each ICT-49 organisation/project will answer the same list of questions in order to have a common structure and make clear each project's goals to the audience
 - h) Joint organisation of a webinar by ICT-49 partners. (Initial thoughts for Q4 2021)

3.2.3 Common Ontologies

An ontology formally describes the set of concepts lying under a specific domain and the association that connects them together²⁶. In order to come up with such a formal explanation, each component needs to be specified as an object or its instance, classes, parameters, and relationships. Moreover, rules, theorems and axioms should be formally specified. Consequently, ontologies provide a reusable knowledge model and incorporate novel knowledge about the domain.

The common ontology for the I-ENERGY project will be designed to cover all the heterogeneous data sources, mainly in the energy domain such as PV, wind, hydropower, smart building, EV, generators, heat, and water. Therefore, the proposed ontology either needs to be built upon existing ontologies or extends current ontologies like BRICK²⁷, HAYSTACK²⁸, BIM²⁹, SAREF³⁰. In any case, a minimum of 3 of the previous well-established vocabularies will be included while designing the ontology. Moreover, the required ontology ensures data interoperability and standardizes semantics on a common set of terms for all the I-ENERGY datasets.

The analysis of the above ontologies and the activities for the definition of the project common ontology has already started within WP3 activities and is based on the currently available data (see deliverable D3.1: '*I-ENERGY Data Interoperability and Processing Management Services (1st technology release)*'), bearing in mind that information provided there will be regularly updated in the successive technology releases: D3.2 and D3.3). Acceleration for the definition of the project ontology could be represented by using what has already been done in this respect in the AI4EU project. An interaction with AI4EU was put in place to try to use the ontology already defined by this project and to understand which terms and modalities it could be extended with I-ENERGY needs. In this respect, I-ENERGY participated in the AI4EU ontology workshop of the 26th March 2021, where AI4EU members presented the project ontology and where, together with other ICT-

²⁶ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ontology_\(information_science\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ontology_(information_science))

²⁷ <https://brickschema.org/>

²⁸ <https://project-haystack.org/doc/docHaystack/Intro>

²⁹ <https://www.bimframework.info/2015/08/bim-ontology.html>

³⁰ <https://saref.etsi.org/>

49 projects, I-ENERGY was invited to present the project requirements to understand what kind of synergies between projects can be implemented. Although the ontology defined for the AI4EU project is much more focused on AI, and I-ENERGY has instead defined a common ontology for heterogeneous data sources in the energy domain, an active collaboration started. Specific online meetings are constantly scheduled, and each ICT-49 project involved in these activities presents its requirements to try to create specific working groups to extend the already existing AI4EU ontology. A common repository to collect all the projects requirements has been created and is constantly updated by AI4EU members with the working group members contributions with the aim of having a common basis on which to work.

3.3 Synergies and Alignment Specifications for Use Cases

In this section, we discuss the synergies and alignment specifications between I-ENERGY and AI4EU. This section starts with an overview of the use-cases. Section 3.3.1 presents the summary of the use cases concisely to make the document self-contained. Only for understanding and documentation purposes, the use cases are divided into different categories. Section 3.3.2

3.3.1 I-ENERGY Requirements (Use Case Summarisation)

In this section, all I-ENERGY use-cases are sorted under general categories to facilitate the documentation process. Figure 11 shows the proposed categories and the corresponding use cases in each of them.

Figure 11: Grouping of I-ENERGY use-cases

3.3.1.1 Data Analysis and Forecasting

The primary purpose of the use cases in this category is to design a platform where usage patterns can be analysed, and users can be notified based on the status of the device, e.g., if the circuit breaker needs some maintenance, then this should be forecasted by using respective AI tools and technologies. The individual use cases for this category are listed below.

Data Analysis and Forecasting	
Use-case Number	Title
UC-1	AI for enhanced network assets predictive maintenance, integrating off-grid data with condition-based monitoring.
UC-6	Cross-functional AI-based predictive analytics to support integrated DSOs assets management and network operation.
UC-7	AI-based consumption and flexibility prediction for local community optimal aggregation and flexibility trading.
UC-9	AI-based IoT enabled PV module-level portfolio optimal predictive maintenance and PV-enhanced industrial plant optimal operation.
UC-11	AI for peer-to-peer renewable energy trading in virtual energy community.
UC-12	AI for Ambient Assisted Living and personal safety/security at home
UC-13	AI for energy-saving efficiency investments de-risking.
UC-14	AI for improved energy performance certificates reliability.
UC-15	AI for predicting the climate change impact in RES and energy demand at the regional level.

Table 1 Use Cases for Category Data Analysis and Forecasting

3.3.1.2 Distribution Network

This category includes the use cases which are related to distribution network load forecasting and optimisation. Networks are an essential part of an IoT system, and we need to handle them carefully to give uninterrupted service to end-users. In our pilot programs, two use cases are made for this service, and they perform tasks such as flexibility assessment and load forecasting. The table given below shows the use cases summarised under this category.

Network

Use-case Number	Title
UC-2	AI for network loads and demand forecasting towards efficient operational planning.
UC-10	AI in EV charging infrastructure.

Table 2 Use Cases for Category Distribution Network

3.3.1.3 Optimisation

This category relates to optimising the energy and non-energy services to enhance user experience with the platform. The use cases related to this category are given below.

Optimisation	
Use-case Number	Title
UC-3	AI for energy demand prediction to optimise District Heating Network (DHN) operation
UC-4	AI for energy-saving verification service, increasing the trust in Energy performance contracts
UC-5	AI for multi-energy system decision support.

Table 3 Use Cases for Category Optimisation

3.3.2 Alignment of I-ENERGY and AI4EU Services

This section thoroughly analyses the AI4EU resources and recommends which of the services and use cases from I-ENERGY may benefit from it. There are many resources shared by leading labs both from academia and industry over the AI4EU platform. The project of AI4EU has evolved over time, and temporary two versions of the AI4EU platforms exist; the old one (<https://www.ai4eu.eu/>), and the new one (<https://www.ai4europe.eu/>). Some resources are already moved to the new platform; however, many resources are in the transition phase and still exist at the old platform. For the sake of completeness, we cover the resources (services and tutorials) from both AI4EU platforms. However, the old site may become obsolete, and the services may no longer be available if decided not to be moved to the new AI4EU platform. The following subsection briefly describes the methodology used to align the AI4EU services

3.3.2.1 Methodology

For aligning the services of I-ENERGY and AI4EU, the first step is the initial investigation of the services and check their relevance. DFKI performed the initial investigation and aligned the services of AI4EU with the use cases of I-ENERGY. This decision is taken in consensus with COMS (responsible for the Deliverable D2.1). The primary reason behind the alignment of AI4EU services with the I-ENERGY use cases is that I-ENERGY services may change over time, and new services

may be introduced. Therefore, in the future, it will be easier to align newly introduced I-ENERGY services with AI4EU services through use cases.

There are a couple of essential aspects to mention here. The first aspect is that the service mapping is merely a recommendation. Therefore, each I-ENERGY service developer shall look closely to check for the usefulness of the corresponding AI4EU service. Secondly, in some cases, the recommended AI4EU service may only fulfil a part of the I-ENERGY requirements.

Following, we discuss the steps of the devised strategy for the alignment.

1. DFKI conducted an initial investigation of the existing AI4EU services.
2. DFKI created an excel sheet that contains the proposal of which use cases of the I-ENERGY are aligned with the services of I-ENERGY.
3. The sheet was sent to all the partners for their feedback.
4. The complete procedure of Partners' feedback incorporation is discussed in detail in Section 3.3.3.
 - a. All the partners voted for one of the four options. These options are: a) service is either useful, b) partially useful, c) 'partner is not sure', or d) the service is not useful.
 - b. Each of the Partners' responses is taken into account as per the excel sheet.
 - c. Suppose a partner commented over only a few services. For other services, the partners' response is categorised as not sure.
5. This step maps the I-ENERGY services to AI4EU services. Table 4 contains the services of I-ENERGY. The first couple of columns are for the service description. The third column contains the usage scenario, and the fourth column describes the use cases where the foreseen AI4EU service is useful. However, it is not straightforward, and it is accomplished with the help of Table 5. Following is the description of how the AI4EU services in column-5 that are mapped to the I-ENERGY services in column-1 of Table 4.
 - a. With the help of partners' feedback, this deliverable accomplishes mapping the AI4EU services to the AI4EU use cases.
 - b. Table 5 provides the AI4EU service and its short description and link in its first three columns, respectively. The complete description of the AI4EU services is given in Section 7.1.
 - c. The fourth column contains the use cases where this service is applicable.
 - d. The fifth column states whether this service is useful or not based on Partners' feedback. If any one of the partners is either fully or partially agrees. The service is labelled as useful. This gives us the mapping of which of the AI4EU services are useful for which use case.
 - e. In Table 4, in column-4, we list all the use cases. The column-5 of Table 4 is filled based on which AI4EU services are useful for which use cases. Therefore, the mapping is complete.

Synergies				
Service	Description	Usage Scenarios	Related Use Cases	AI4EU Services
S1	Visual analytics dashboard for electricity consumption centres	5.1, 5.2, 5.3, & 5.4	5	AI4EU-S5
S2	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres	5.1, 5.2, 5.3 & 5.4	5	AI4EU-S5
S3	Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement	14.1, 14.2 & 14.3	14	--
S4	Energy Performance Certificate data exploitation	14.4, 14.5 & 14.6	14	--
S5	Climate change solar radiation forecasting	15.1	15	AI4EU-S10
S6	Digital Twin: DER simulation for supporting system-level scenario evaluation	3.2, 3.5	3, 7	AI4EU-S4, AI4EU-S5
S7	Predictive Maintenance Analytics	6.1, 6.2	1, 4, 6	AI4EU-S1, AI4EU-S2,
S8	Measurement and verification of energy savings	4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, 4.6, 4.7, 4.8, 4.9*, 4.10, 4.11	4	-
S9	Energy flexibility forecasting	3.2, 3.5, 3.7, 3.8, 3.10, 3.11, 6.1	6, 7, 8, 11, 12	AI4EU-S1, AI4EU-S2, AI4EU-S4,
S10	Energy load/consumption/demand forecasting	3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 6.1	2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 11, 12	AI4EU-S1, AI4EU-S2, AI4EU-S3, AI4EU-S4, AI4EU-S5,
S11	AI for energy demand prediction to optimise DHN operation	3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7,	3	AI4EU-S4, AI4EU-S5

		3.8, 3.9, 3.10 & 3.15		
S12	Optimisation of the production mix	5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.6 & 5.11	5	AI4EU-S5
S13	I-ENERGY Virtual Workbench - Marketplace (catalogue of ML models and Data sources to facilitate the creation of new application)	3.6, 3.7	6, 7	AI4EU-S1, AI4EU-S2
S14	Activity recognition and forecasting	3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8	3, 7, 8, 11	AI4EU-S1, AI4EU-S2, AI4EU-S3, AI4EU-S4, AI4EU-S5
S15	Anomalous behaviour detection	3.10, 3.11	3, 8, 11	AI4EU-S2, AI4EU-S4, AI4EU-S5,
S16	Blockchain Hybrid energy data storage	Not available	7, 8	AI4EU-S1, AI4EU-S3, AI4EU-S4

Table 4 Mapping of I-ENERGY Services to I-ENERGY use cases and AI4EU Services.

AI4EU Services				
Service Number	Title	Link	Use Case	Useful for INERGY
AI4EU-S1	Deep Autoencoders for Anomaly Detection	https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/deep-autoencoders-anomaly-detection	1,2,6,7,9	Yes
AI4EU-S2	VisioRed	https://www.ai4europa.eu/research/ai-catalog/visioRed	1,6,9,11	Yes
AI4EU-S3	Time prediction for flexible manufacturing	https://www.ai4europa.eu/research/ai-catalog/time-prediction-flexible-manufacturing	2,8	Yes
AI4EU-S4	Pump Failure Prediction	https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/pump-failure-prediction	3,8	Yes
AI4EU-S5	RL4Machine Tuning	https://www.ai4europa.eu/research/ai-catalog/rl4machinetuning	3,5	Yes
AI4EU-S6	Q-RUL	https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/q-rul	4	No
AI4EU-S7	HOPS	https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/hops	5	Yes
AI4EU-S8	MPC-NODE	https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/mpc-node	11	No
AI4EU-S9	Urban4Cast	https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/urban4cast	15	No
AI4EU-S10	VerifiAI	https://www.ai4europa.eu/research/ai-catalog/verifai	15	Yes
AI4EU-S11	AI Industry Tutorial	https://www.ai4europa.eu/research/ai-catalog/ai-industry-tutorial-04	7	Yes

Table 5 Mapping of AI4EU Services to AI4EU Use Case

3.3.3 Template

The purpose of this section is to present services and models along with feedback from our partners on whether the following service is helpful in our use case or not. The template for associating the I-ENERGY use cases with AI4EU is given below. It

- We have given four options to our partners, out of which they can select which is best suitable to our use case. The four options are explained below.
 - Yes: If the partner thinks that the resource is helpful for the use case.
 - No: If the partner thinks that the resource is not helpful for the use case.
 - Partially Agreed: If the partner thinks that some resource can be used without a use case.
 - Not sure: If the partner is unsure about the usefulness of the current resource for the use case.

Use Case-1 Title of the use case

Associated Pilot Number of the use case

Use Case Description

This section aims at providing a brief description related to the use case. It also includes what the aim of the use case is.

Related Service from AI4EU

The corresponding service number from the old AI4EU platform is given here.

Partners' Feedback.

- 1) Yes
 - a) Partner's Name
- 2) Partially Agreed
 - a) Partner's Name
- 3) Not Sure
 - a) Partner's Name
- 4) No
 - a) Partner's Name

Related Service from AI4EU New website

The corresponding service number from the new AI4EU platform is given here.

Partners' Feedback

- 5) Yes
 - a) Partner's Name
- 6) Partially Agreed

- a) Partner's Name
- 7) Not Sure
- a) Partner's Name
- 8) No
- a) Partner's Name

3.3.1 Example

Following the structure given in section 3.3.3, we also show an example for one of the use cases. For feedback on more use cases, please refer to Appendix2.

Use Case-1 AI for enhanced network assets predictive maintenance, integrating off-grid data with condition-based monitoring

Pilot No. 1

Use Case Description

This use case refers to the detection and automatic analysis of faults in circuit breakers. This use case aims to form a detailed analysis supported by visualisations if possible and notify related authorities.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S1 (Deep Autoencoders for Anomaly Detection)

Partners' Feedback

- 9) Yes
 - a) ICCS, CARTIF
- 10) Partially Agreed
 - a) None
- 11) Not Sure
 - a) None
- 12) No
 - a) None

Related Service from AI4EU New website

AI4EU-S2(VisioRed)

Partners' Feedback

- 13) Yes
 - a) ICCS
- 14) Partially Agreed
 - a) None
- 15) Not Sure
 - a) None
- 16) No

a) None

The example above shows the deployed resource present at the AI4EU platform and contains services that can be utilised for I-ENERGY. A complete description of all the use cases is provided in Appendix 2, specifically in Section 7.2.

4 Onboarding and Deployment of I-ENERGY Assets for AI4EU

This section describes how the specifications and guidelines of the I-ENERGY components are onboarded and deployed using the AI4EU platform. First, section 4.1 gives an overview of the general deployment guidelines that each of the I-ENERGY components must follow to be deployed at the AI4EU platform. Next, section 4.2 describes the process of onboarding. Finally, section 4.3 shows the local deployment process of electricity consumption prediction example.

4.1 Specifications of I-ENERGY Components for AI4EU Experiments

The experimental environment of AI4EU Experiments enables us to use and publish AI modules in a development environment equipped with validation and evaluation components. Furthermore, the AI4EU Experiments facilitate the users to build customised AI pipelines by employing the intuitive graphical user interface. The customised pipelines can be utilised not only for commercial purposes but also for learning and experimentation. Moreover, AI4EU Experiments aim to develop a collaborative environment in which the users advance their AI pipelines by exploiting the resources available in the AI community. To serve this purpose, I-ENERGY is targeting to develop services that provide an abstraction for a set of AI models and data processing methods. Thus, these resources are accessible for the AI community to be reused and even enhanced further.

Figure 12 Visual description of I-ENERGY assets deployment process to AI4EU Experiments

Figure 12 exhibits the I-ENERGY process of developing a pipeline using the AI4EU Experiments platform. Moreover, it describes the components that will be sharable on AI4EU Experiments and abstracted by the wrapper services. The I-ENERGY components need to be dockerised for onboarding to AI4EU Experiments such that they become reusable and interoperable blocks for AI pipelines. The containerised applications should use Protocol Buffers (protobuf) Language (proto3 syntax) to define the public service methods exposed via gRPC. These service methods will be defined in a model.proto file that operates on protobuf language. There will not be any external imports associated with the container.

Once the I-ENERGY models are successfully onboarded and published to the marketplace, they will be publically available to the AI community to create their customised pipelines on AI4EU design studio (Acu-Compose).

The specifications for the onboarding of I-ENERGY assets through AI4EU Experiments are elaborated as follows:

- The components of I-ENERGY should consider reusability and interoperability for creating AI pipelines in AI4EU Acu-Compose while designing the components.
- All the developed assets of I-ENERGY should be sharable and dockerised in the AI4EU Experiments Container format.
- The public service methods of the I-ENERGY assets should be defined using protobuf (proto 3 syntax) and implemented using gRPC framework.
- All the RPC methods present in an I-ENERGY container should be defined in a single proto file present in the same service block.
- Both the functional and non-functional testing should be carried out before publishing the wrapped I-ENERGY component.
- The I-ENERGY services should be scalable and available all the time. If there are some limitations, they need to be comprehensively elaborated in the documentation.
- The I-ENERGY components should be appropriately documented before their publication.
- Before publication, all the I-ENERGY models accessible in AI4EU Experiments should be assessed against General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and an assessment list for Trustworthy AI.
- The published I-ENERGY models in AI4EU Experiments will be tracked and updated accordingly during the entire tenure of the project.

It is essential to mention that before publishing each I-ENERGY asset, it will be made sure that it follows the constraints of reusability and interoperability. Furthermore, each asset should be published so that the European AI community can consume it through direct service. Moreover, the consortium will ensure that assets satisfy the AI4EU requirements of publication. Therefore, it is mandatory to specify the following metadata for each of the asset I-ENERGY assets:

Title and Description:

The publishable I-ENERGY asset needs to have a proper title name and a short description stating the asset's functionality.

Images from the Asset:

It is essential to have few images attached that can illustrate the normal functioning of the asset.

Maintainers Information and Contact Details:

The information of the developer or the maintainer, who will ensure the sustainability of the asset, needs to be included. Furthermore, the contact details of the support team are mandatory.

License:

Each publishable asset should have a defined licence stating whether it is open-source or used for specific purposes only.

Main Characteristics:

The main purpose and characteristics of the asset should be clearly defined before deploying the asset on AI4EU Resource Catalogue.

Documentation:

Each asset that is about to be deployed should be well documented. All the details about the installation, setting up, pre-requisites, and usage examples should be clearly elaborated in the documentation. Moreover, depending upon the asset, all the required documents should be accompanied before publication.

GDPR Compliance and Trustworthy AI:

All the assets that are about to be deployed will be completely evaluated whether they are GDPR compliant according to the guidelines described in I-ENERGY AI Ethics Guide [3]. Moreover, each asset will be inspected against the assessment list for Trustworthy AI. The specification for the deployment of I-ENERGY assets to the AI4EU resource catalogue is explained as follows:

1. The I-ENERGY sharable assets need to be wrapped in a format that can be reusable by the members of the AI community as a service, docker image, executable files, etc.
2. Apart from reusability, the I-ENERGY assets need to have interoperability by complying with the existing metadata standard and ontologies.
3. Both the functional and non-functional testing should be carried out before publishing the wrapped I-ENERGY assets.
4. Apart from the simple playground purposes and simple data pipelines provided by the AI4EU, all the assets will be executed in our local environment.
5. It is the responsibility of the I-ENERGY to ensure scalability and availability of the published services and communicated clearly in case of any limitations.
6. All the required information needs to be in AI4EU catalogue metadata, such as description, installation guidelines, license, terms of usage, maintenance information, etc.
7. All the I-ENERGY sharable assets shall be assessed against GDPR compliance and the assessment list for Trustworthy AI before the publication.
8. The published assets shall be frequently monitored for potential changes throughout the complete tenure of the project.

4.2 Onboarding of Resources

4.2.1 Onboarding of Models

This section discusses how one can upload (onboard) a model to AI4EU Experiments. The example of Electricity Consumption [5] makes it easier for the reader to understand. The chosen example uses regression for modelling the forecasting problem. Regression³¹ is a statistical technique for determining the relationship between the dependent variable, electricity consumption, with the help of predictor variables. The model chosen to be deployed on the AI4EU Experiments platform for testing purposes utilises the Random Forest tree regressor [6] from scikit learn [7]. It grows various trees using the data features and then performs prediction by performing majority voting over all the trees. In the case of regression, it takes the mean value of all the predictions given by the trees and uses it as the final prediction.

The dataset used for the electricity consumption example is publicly available in Germany's Open Power System data [8]. It contains electricity consumption, wind power production, and solar power production for 2006–2017. It is time-series data, and it has been used from 2006-2016 as a training set and 2017 as a test set. After defining the train and test split, some data pre-processing steps are performed. These steps include cleaning the rows containing missing values and converting them to individual formats. The pre-processed data is further used for training and testing the model.

4.2.1.1 Required Tools

Following are the required tools for model onboarding:

- Python: The user needs to install the latest Python (refer to appendix python) version to run the demo application. The example provided is developed using Python (Section 6.3).
- gRPC: It is used to facilitate the communication between users and servers. The user will request the prediction through the gRPC server (Section 2.3.1.3).
- Protocol Buffer file: The protocol buffer file is used to generate gRPC classes for Python.
- Docker: The Solution contains a predictive model along with server and protobuff files. Docker is used for packaging the solution into a single image file that can be used for onboarding onto the AI4EU Experiments platform (Section 2.3.1.1).

4.2.1.2 Steps for Model Onboarding

There are two ways to onboard the models at the AI4EU Experiments platform. The first way is to train a model over a dataset and upload it to the Platform. The second way is to provide the model configurations with required training data. Either way, it is required to make a Service file (as described below in Step 1) to handle the model and datasets.

Figure 13 depicts all the steps of onboarding the model to the AI4EU platform. Step 1 illustrates that how to create a model service file. Once the model service file is created, in the next step (Step 2), the model input and output interfaces are specified in the protocol buffer file. In Step 3, this protocol buffer file is used to generate the gRPC server and client stubs. These stubs are the

³¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Regression_analysis

empty implementation of the client and server with known interfaces. Next, the user must implement the specific methods for the service. In Step 4 and Step 5, these client and server stubs are implemented for the electricity consumption forecast service as discussed above. Following the guidelines provided in Section 4.1, the complete solution must be dockerised as discussed in Step 6 and Step 7. It is described in detail how to dockerise and register the docker in a docker registry such that AI4EU Experiments can find it via a URL provided by the Docker registry. Finally, Step 8 describes how to complete the onboarding process by filling in the required information in a form. A detailed description of all of the steps mentioned above for onboarding a model is given below.

Figure 13 Steps for uploading the model to the AI4EU platform

Step 1 Create Service for loading and training models

The Service file encapsulates all of the functions which are used in the server. In the example provided, the Service file contains a prediction function. The function receives the input from the user and sends the prediction as a response to the user. Service file can also be used to train the model on the new data transmitted by the client. Depending upon the application, the contents of the Service file can vary.

In the case of a pre-trained model, i.e., the model is already trained on the dataset, the Service file loads the weight file of the model (the model in serialised format) and contains a function that performs the prediction. The example code snippet for such a case is given below in Figure 14.

```
import joblib
import pandas as pd

#Loading the pre-trained Scikit-Learn Model
model = joblib.load("best_model.sav")

#Predicting the Electricity Consumption based on test data.
def predict_consumption (Yesterday, Yesterday_Diff):

    X_test = pd.DataFrame({"Yesterday":Yesterday, "Yesterday_Diff": Yesterday_Diff})
    prediction = model.predict(X_test)
    return(prediction)
```

Figure 14 Code snippet for defining a Service that loads a pre-trained model and performs predictions.

In the second case, where we do not have a pre-trained model, the user needs to train it at their cluster or machine. The Service file defines the model with training datasets. It also contains the functionality to train and test the model. It is also possible to define the model in a separate file and import it into the Service. In the case of a Deep Neural Network, dataset batches are defined in this file (Figure 15).

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np

# Read the data and store in a dataframe called training_set
train_data_path = 'train.csv'
training_set = pd.read_csv(train_data_path)

# Select the target variable and call it y
y = training_set.SalePrice

# Create a list of the predictor variables
predictors = ["MSSubClass", "LotArea", "YearBuilt", "BedroomAbvGr",
              "TotRmsAbvGrd"]

# Create a new dataframe with the predictors list
X = training_set[predictors]

# Import DecisionTreeRegressor
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor

# Define the first model
tree_model = DecisionTreeRegressor()

# Fit model
tree_model.fit(X, y)

def predict_sale_price(MSSubClass, LotArea, YearBuilt, BedroomAbvGr,
                       TotRmsAbvGrd):
    prediction = tree_model.predict([[MSSubClass, LotArea, YearBuilt,
                                      BedroomAbvGr, TotRmsAbvGrd]])
    return (prediction)
```

Figure 15 Code snippet for defining a Service that trains a model and performs predictions.

Step 2 Create protocol buffer file

The second step is to define a protocol buffer file (file with ".proto" extension). "Protocol buffer is Google's language-neutral, platform-neutral, extensible mechanism for serialising structured data just like XML, but smaller, faster, and more straightforward"³². It allows us to define our model's structure, i.e., input and output in a single file. Furthermore, it can quickly generate the source code files from structure definition to read and write the data from various data streams. It also allows us to choose the language of our choice, making it much easier to define. The protobuf file for the electricity consumption model is depicted in Figure 16.

```

syntax = "proto3";

message Features {
  repeated float Yesterday = 1;
  repeated float Yesterday_Diff = 2;
}

message Prediction {
  repeated float Consumption = 1;
}

service Predict {
  rpc predict_consumption(Features) returns (Prediction);
}
    
```

Figure 16 Protobuf file for our Electricity Consumption model.

The syntax must be defined for the "proto3" version because the earlier versions are obsolete. It is also required to define features and prediction attributes with suitable data types. In the end, we call the Service prediction method with the features to receive the prediction. In the example above, there is a number assigned to each of the features. Please note that these numbers indicate serialising the features and are automatically assigned.

Step 3 Configuration of gRPC with Protocol Buffer

The third step includes the configuration of gRPC with the protobuf file that was created in Step 2. Server and client can be defined on different machines. In gRPC, the client application invokes the server application as if it is a local object via predefined defined functions. Therefore it becomes easier to create a distributed applications and services. As in many RPC systems, gRPC is based on defining a service as of Step 1. It specifies the methods that can be called remotely with their parameters and return types. The server implements the interface defined in the protobuf file and runs a gRPC server to handle client calls on the server-side. On the client side, there is a client stub that contains the same placeholder as the server. It is important to mention that the client stub is just referred to as client in some languages.

gRPC uses the protocol buffer compiler, protoc, to generate code from a defined proto file: it automatically generates gRPC client and server code, as well as the regular protocol buffer code for populating, serialising, and retrieving defined message types (Figure 17).

³² <https://developers.google.com/protocol-buffers>

```
#First install gRPCio
python3 -m pip install grpcio

#Then install gRPC tools
python3 -m pip install grpcio-tools googleapis-common-protos

#Generate the stubs to create client/server

python3 -m grpc_tools.protoc -I. --python_out=. --grpc_python_out=. model.proto
```

Figure 17 Commands for Installing and configuring gRPC.

The files generated by gRPC, along with their descriptions, are given below.

- i) model_pb2.py contains the messages classes.
 - (1) model_pb2.Features for the input features
 - (2) model_pb2.Prediction for the prediction price.

- ii) model_pb2_grpc.py contains server and client classes
 - (1) model_pb2_grpc.PredictServicer will be used by the server
 - (2) model_pb2_grpc.PredictStub will be used by the client.

Step 4 Create gRPC server

The next step creates the gRPC server using the stub generated in step 3. The server imports the generated files and the function. The imported function handles the predictions. For the current example, the model predicts electricity consumption. First, however, a class needs to be defined that receives a request from the client and uses the prediction function to return the response. This class is known as Server. The user makes the request that contains the input features in the request body. These features are then parsed at the server-side and sent to the model for prediction. For example, in our case, the user will send past electricity data (input features) and receive the model's forecast (prediction).

```
import grpc
from concurrent import futures
import time
import model_pb2
import model_pb2_grpc
import service as pred

port = 8061

class PredictServicer(model_pb2_grpc.PredictServicer):

    def predict_consumption(self, request, context):

        response = model_pb2.Prediction()

        response.Consumption[:] = pred.predict_consumption(request.Yesterday, request.Yesterday_Diff)

        return response

server = grpc.server(futures.ThreadPoolExecutor(max_workers = 10))
model_pb2_grpc.add_PredictServicer_to_server (PredictServicer(),server)
print("Starting server. Listening on the port : " + str(port))
server.add_insecure_port("[::]:{}".format(port))
server.start()
```

Figure 18 Code snippet for our gRPC Server file.

The name of the server class is PredictServicer class, as depicted in Figure 18. This class parses the input received from the client. The parsed input is passed to the model, which makes a prediction. After the model has made the prediction, the response will be returned to the client. One thing to note here is that server is running on localhost. However, if the model needs to be deployed onto some external server or cluster, the IP or web address of the server along with the relevant port needs to be given to the PredictServicer function.

The necessary functions, i.e., add_PredictServicer_to_server, are imported from the "model_pb2_grpc.py" file generated in step 3, and the prediction function is passed as an argument. The next step is to start a gRPC server such that clients can use the service. The gRPC server runs on port 8061, whereas an optional HTTP-Server for a Web-UI for user interaction runs on port 8062.

Step 5 Create gRPC Client

This step demonstrates the development of the client. This client will invoke the methods present at the server. Figure 19 shows the example code snippet of the gRPC client. As per the code, the user needs to first define the address of the deployed server. After that, we shall open a gRPC channel and create the stub using the generated gRPC files. Finally, the client is ready, and it needs to create a request message with the data.

```
import pandas as pd
import sklearn.metrics as metrics
import numpy as np
import grpc
from random import randint
from timeit import default_timer as timer
import model_pb2
import model_pb2_grpc

start_ch = timer()
port_addr = 'localhost:8061'
channel = grpc.insecure_channel(port_addr)
stub = model_pb2_grpc.PredictStub(channel)
end_ch = timer()
prediction = model_pb2.Features(Yesterday = X_test["Yesterday"].values, Yesterday_Diff= X_test["Yesterday_Diff"].values)
response = stub.predict_consumption(prediction)
response = pd.DataFrame({"Consumption":response.Consumption})
print("The prediction is ", response )
```

Figure 19 Code snippet for our gRPC Client file.

Step 6 Dockerisation of Model

The model configurations are now complete, and we are ready to package our model into a dockerised [9] format. To package the model into the dockerised format, we first need to create the Docker image. A Docker image comprises a set of instructions for the docker container. The instructions include application code, dependencies, libraries and other important information for running an application. Docker images can have multiple different layers which originate from the previous layer. For example, Figure 20 shows the Docker file used to create a docker image for the electricity price prediction application.

```
FROM ubuntu:18.04

MAINTAINER Danish "danish.nazir@dfki.de"

RUN apt-get update -y
RUN apt-get install -y python3-pip python3-dev
RUN pip3 install --upgrade pip
RUN pip3 install numpy
RUN pip3 install pandas
RUN pip3 install sklearn
RUN pip3 install numpy
RUN pip3 install joblib

WORKDIR /

COPY ./requirements.txt /requirements.txt
RUN pip3 install -r requirements.txt

RUN useradd app
USER app
COPY model.proto model_pb2.py model_pb2_grpc.py client_pred.py service.py prediction.py best_model.sav ./
COPY . /

ENTRYPOINT ["python3","prediction.py"]
```

Figure 20 Docker for Electricity Consumption prediction model.

The commands for copying all code files to the Docker container are specified within the docker file. It is important to note that whenever any layer is rebuilt, all the layers that follow it in the Dockerfile will also be rebuilt. It is a good practice to separate the application dependency from the gRPC dependency. Therefore, it is important to separate the gRPC specific requirements in a file called requirements.txt (Figure 21). Hence, gRPC will be a separate layer when the Docker image is built. Thus, it avoids rebuilding this layer every time a change is made in the application.

```
# GRPC Python setup requirements
coverage>=4.0
cython>=0.29.8
enum34>=1.0.4
protobuf>=3.5.0.post1
six>=1.10
wheel>=0.29
grpcio-tools
```

Figure 21 gRPC Installation requirements saved in requirements.txt file

Step 7 Deployment of Docker:

After creating the Docker image, it is uploaded to a Docker image repository. A unique URL is created by the repository that can be used to link the model with AI4EU Experiments. One such Platform is the docker hub; the user can create an account before pushing the docker images to the Platform. The signup URL is <https://hub.docker.com/>. However, the user can use any other docker image repository. Figure 22 depicts the required commands for pushing the docker image to the docker.io platform.

```
#Build the docker Image

docker build -f Dockerfile -t dn8034/electricity-consumption:latest .

#Login to Docker.io

docker login docker.io

# Run the docker Image.

docker push docker.io/dn8034/electricity-consumption:latest
```

Figure 22 Pushing Docker Image to Docker.io portal.

Step 8 Upload solution to AI4EU Experiments:

As described above, A URL is provided by the docker hub once the user pushes the docker image. AI4EU Experiments uses this URL for accessing the complete solution. Navigating to the AI4EU Experiments platform, the user selects the ON-BOARDING-MODEL option, as shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23 Onboarding of Electricity Consumption model.

The user will select an appropriate Model Name and fill in the URL given by the docker registry in the Host field name. Next, the user needs to add the Image URL provided by the docker image repository to the Image field and the image tag. The user has already created a protobuf file in Step 2 that will be uploaded. The user also needs to specify a licence that is an optional field. However, to comply with GDRP directions, it is better to specify a licence. In case the user wants to specify the licence, a licence file must be uploaded as well. It is the last step to complete the onboarding process. Once the user submits the completed form, the uploaded model will go through the review process. After the review process, the model will be uploaded to the AI4EU platform. To verify that onboarding was successful, the user can view the Status in the onboarding history and then inspect the onboarding-logs text file inside the model artefacts section. In case of successful onboarding, a signature will be created. This signature also contains the protobuf file.

4.2.2 Onboarding of Data Sources

The dataset is uploaded as a model to the AI4EU Experiments platform, which refers to the Data Sources section³³. It provides the data for the models. The onboarding steps are the same as described except for the gRPC server. Instead of performing the predictions, the server will now read the data from the data source. The data source can be anything, e.g., CSV files, images, video files. However, in the electricity consumption forecast example, it is a CSV file.

The data sources class implements the `get_next_rowService` class, which has a method that defines "get_next_row", which will fetch the rows from the CSV (Figure 24). Next, it needs to set the respective gRPC status codes to handle user requests. It sets the gRPC status code `NOT_FOUND` or `OUT_OF_RANGE` if all the data rows have already been processed. The data source service, being the starting point of the pipeline, is called an empty message according to the implementation of the generic orchestrator. After successfully onboarding the data source, it can be imported into the AI4EU Experiments pipeline and can be connected to the model, as shown in section 4.3.1.3.

³³ <https://acumos-int-fhg.ai4eu.eu/#/marketPlace#marketplaceTemplate>

```
import grpc
from concurrent import futures
import time
import databroker_pb2
import databroker_pb2_grpc
import get_next_row as gnr

port = 8061
row_obj = gnr.FetchRowCSV()
current_row = 0

class get_next_rowServicer(databroker_pb2_grpc.get_next_rowServicer):
    def get_next_row(self, request, context):
        response = databroker_pb2.Features()
        total_rows = row_obj.init_count()
        current_row = row_obj.current_row
        if current_row == total_rows:
            context.set_code(grpc.StatusCode.NOT_FOUND)
            context.set_details('All available data has been processed')
        else:
            row = row_obj.get_next_row(current_row)
            response.Yesterday = row[0]
            response.Yesterday_Diff = row[1]
            row_obj.current_row = row_obj.current_row + 1

        return response

# create a grpc server :
server = grpc.server(futures.ThreadPoolExecutor(max_workers=10))

databroker_pb2_grpc.add_get_next_rowServicer_to_server(get_next_rowServicer(), server)
print("Starting Server. Listening to port : " + str(port))
server.add_insecure_port("[::]:{}".format(port))
server.start()

try:
    while True:
        time.sleep(86400)
except KeyboardInterrupt:
    server.stop(0)
```

Figure 24 Databroker for Electricity Consumption prediction example.

4.2.3 Onboarding of Jupyter Notebook

It is not part of the onboarding process for the electricity consumption example. However, for the sake of completeness, this process is described. JupyterLab³⁴ is a web-based interactive development environment for Jupyter notebooks, code, and data. It is flexible, configurable, and permits to arrange the user interface to support a wide range of workflows in data science, scientific computing, and machine learning. In addition, JupyterLab is extensible and modular and allows to write plugins that add new components and integrate with existing ones.

Uploading the Jupyter notebook is also like uploading the model and data source on the AI4EU Experiments platform. First, the creation of a gRPC server is required for handling users' requests. Then, users can run the Jupyter Notebook that will communicate with the gRPC server

³⁴ <https://jupyter.org/>

for execution. It is assumed that the model and data source are already published on the AI4EU Experiments platform.

4.3 Deployment of AI4EU Experiments Pipeline Using Local Platform

This section is divided into two parts. Section 4.3.1 explains different components of the Design Studio to show how an AI pipeline is created at the AI4EU platform. Since, at the moment, only local deployment is possible, section 4.3.2 explains the steps for the local deployment. Figure 25 shows the interface of the Design Studio.

Figure 25 Screenshot illustrating the outline of AI4EU Design Studio

The design studio has three main components (Models, Data Transform Tools, and Data Sources) explained in the following sections.

4.3.1.1 Models

The Model Component provides the trained models which are available for the various tasks. We can simply select a model through drag and drop. Figure 26 shows the screenshot for the Model component.

Figure 26 Screenshot illustrating the Model component in AI4EU Design Studio

4.3.1.2 Data Transform Tools

The data transformation tool enables the user to convert the input data into a required format that the model can utilize. Analogous to the Model component, the data transformation tool can be employed with a simple drag and drop. The Data Transformation Tool is presented in Figure 27. Please note that for the electricity consumption prediction problem, no data transformation component is required.

Figure 27 Visual exhibition of data transform tools component in Acumos Visual design studio.

4.3.1.3 Data Sources

With the help of the Data Sources Component, we can integrate data for any model by dragging the component into the canvas. For example, figure 28 depicts the data source component from Design Studio:

Figure 28 Visual exhibition of data sources tools component in Acumos Design Studio

It is important to mention that the nodes can only connect when the input parameter on one side matches the output of the other side. Moreover, the design studio is intelligent enough to

highlight a possible match between two nodes. An example of a complete pipeline solution of electricity consumption prediction is explained in Figure 29.

Figure 29 Graphical illustration of the sample pipeline.

In the above figure, there are two nodes connected to each other responsible for providing various services. For example, the 'electricity consumption dataset' node provides the dataset to the 'electricity consumption model' node that predicts the future electricity consumption based on the past data.

Once the solution is ready, the user can click on deploy at the top right and export the model locally by downloading the solution as a zip file, as illustrated in Figure 30.

Figure 30 Graphical guidance of the deployment of the created pipeline.

4.3.2 Local Deployment of Applications

This section explains how the solution can be deployed locally on the Kubernetes. Please refer to Appendix 1 to set up the local environment. The eight (8) steps for deploying application on Kubernetes are explained below:

- 1) Extract the downloaded solutions.zip.
- 2) Create a namespace with the following command:
`kubectl create namespace $namespace_name`
 e.g., `kubectl create namespace electricity_example`
- 3) Run the Kubernetes client script with the following command:
`python kubernetes-client-script.py -n electricity_example`

Make sure that your python environment is activated and install the necessary modules; if not; run the following commands:

```
pip install grpcio
pip install pyYAML
pip install protobuf
```

- 4) Write down/store the Node IP address [address] and the Orchestrator Port [port] that are printed in the last two lines of the output of the previous command highlighted in Figure 31.


```
get namespaces: output NAME          STATUS   AGE
default          Active   20h
kube-node-lease  Active   20h
kube-public      Active   20h
kube-system      Active   20h
subduku          Active   20h
type <class 'str'>
Given namespace is active
web_ui_service file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-gui_service.yaml node_port = 30001
added webui service
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-gui_service_webui.yaml
set_node_port to /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-gui_service_webui.yaml to 30001
apply get ['service/subduku-tutorial-guiwebui', 'configured']
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-gui_service.yaml
set_node_port to /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-gui_service.yaml to 30000
apply get ['service/subduku-tutorial-gui', 'configured']
web_ui_service file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-design-evaluator1_service.yaml node_port = 30003
added webui service
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-design-evaluator1_service_webui.yaml
set_node_port to /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-design-evaluator1_service_webui.yaml to 30003
apply get ['service/subduku-tutorial-design-evaluatorwebui', 'configured']
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-design-evaluator1_service.yaml
set_node_port to /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-design-evaluator1_service.yaml to 30002
apply get ['service/subduku-tutorial-design-evaluator', 'configured']
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/aspolver-clingo-oneshot1_deployment.yaml
apply get ['deployment.apps/aspolver-clingo-oneshot1', 'unchanged']
web_ui_service file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/aspolver-clingo-oneshot1_service.yaml node_port = 30005
added webui service
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/aspolver-clingo-oneshot1_service_webui.yaml
set_node_port to /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/aspolver-clingo-oneshot1_service_webui.yaml to 30005
apply get ['service/aspolver-clingo-oneshotwebui', 'configured']
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/aspolver-clingo-oneshot1_service.yaml
set_node_port to /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/aspolver-clingo-oneshot1_service.yaml to 30004
apply get ['service/aspolver-clingo-oneshot1', 'configured']
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/orchestrator_deployment.yaml
apply get ['deployment.apps/orchestrator', 'unchanged']
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-gui_deployment.yaml
apply get ['deployment.apps/subduku-tutorial-gui', 'unchanged']
web_ui_service file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/orchestrator_service.yaml node_port = 30007
added webui service
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/orchestrator_service_webui.yaml
set_node_port to /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/orchestrator_service_webui.yaml to 30007
apply get ['service/orchestratorwebui', 'configured']
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/orchestrator_service.yaml
set_node_port to /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/orchestrator_service.yaml to 30005
apply get ['service/orchestrator', 'configured']
apply deployment_services file_name = /home/hasini/Desktop/dfki_work/ai-eu/subduku/deployments/subduku-tutorial-design-evaluator1_deployment.yaml
apply get ['deployment.apps/subduku-tutorial-design-evaluator1', 'unchanged']
('subduku-tutorial-guiwebui': 30001, 'subduku-tutorial-gui': 30000, 'subduku-tutorial-design-evaluatorwebui': 30003, 'subduku-tutorial-design-evaluator': 30002, 'aspolver-clingo-oneshotwebui': 30005, 'aspolver-clingo-oneshot1': 30004, 'orchestratorwebui': 30007, 'orchestrator': 30005)
start updating the docker info than
update_node_ports: [{'container_name': 'aspolver-clingo-oneshot1', 'ip_address': 'aspolver-clingo-oneshot1', 'port': 30004}, {'container_name': 'subduku-tutorial-design-evaluator1', 'ip_address': 'subduku-tutorial-design-evaluator1', 'port': 30002}, {'container_name': 'subduku-tutorial-gui', 'ip_address': 'subduku-tutorial-gui', 'port': 30000}, {'container_name': 'orchestrator', 'ip_address': 'orchestrator', 'port': 30005}]
Docker info file is successfully updated
node IP address : 192.168.22.210
orchestrator Port is : 30005
```

Figure 31 Screenshot indicating IP address and port that needs to be used later.

- 5) `cd orchestrator_client`
- 6) `python orchestrator_client.py [address]: [port]`

- 7) In order to run the script for endless time, you can run the following command:

```
while sleep 1;  
do python orchestrator_client.py [address]: [port];  
done
```

- 8) Once the orchestration client is ready, minikube can be used to access the web interface with the following command:

```
kubectl -n $namespace_name$ get node, service -o wide
```

To view the logs of the pipeline execution user can use the following command:

- View logs of orchestrator pod.

```
kubectl logs -n $namespace_name$ $orchestrator_pod_name
```

In case of Issues, you can inspect the Status of your pods by running the following commands:

- Get all the pods in a namespace

```
kubectl get pods --namespace $namespace_name$
```
- Describe specific Pod

```
kubectl describe -n $namespace_name$ pod $pod$
```
- Describe Reason of Fail for specific Pod

```
kubectl describe -n $namespace_name$ pod $pod$ | grep -A 3 Events
```

5 Conclusion

The scope of the deliverable was to provide the foundation in terms of guidelines for further development and deployment of AI models and services identified within the I-ENERGY project to the AI4EU platform. Furthermore, its goal was also to provide Synergies & Alignment between I-ENERGY and AI4EU. To fulfil these goals, it systematically described the necessary components of the AI4EU platform (Section 2).

Furthermore, the alignment and cross-fertilisation between I-ENERGY and AI4EU are explored both at the strategic and use case levels. On the one hand, this report discusses the high-level synergies in terms of open calls, dissemination and common ontologies. On the other hand, it focuses explicitly on the alignment of I-ENERGY and AI4EU services. To this end, this deliverable describes the methodology devised for the alignment of services in both projects. Identified AI4EU services were circulated to partners for their feedback to validate the correctness of these alignments.

In order to provide a guideline with the practical knowledge of creating, assembling, and deploying I-ENERGY models, a simple energy consumption prediction model was created, onboarded, and deployed over AI4EU Experiments. The insights of this process have been incorporated into Section 4 specifically regarding local deployment since AI4EU does not currently offer the resources for online deployment.

The main outcome of these steps is a set of guidelines for the creation and deployment process and the synergies between AI4EU and I-ENERGY to facilitate the deployment of models and pipelines for I-ENERGY partners. Also, it prevents reinventing the wheel since already existing services from AI4EU can be re-used. Nevertheless, the AI4EU project is currently undergoing many changes during the writing of this deliverable, and in the future, there will be significant modifications to it. The I-ENERGY project will follow these updates in the future closely in a daily basis as part of Task 2.4 (Specifications of I-ENERGY - AI4EU Cross-fertilisation, Synergies and Alignment).

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6 Appendix 1

This section discusses the prerequisites essential for the successful local deployment of AI4EU solutions.

Specific Requirements:

To deploy a solution locally, some components need to be installed first, which are mentioned below:

1. Docker
2. Kubernetes Cluster
3. Python

6.1 Docker

To install docker [9], we first need to make sure that our OS is updated, which can be checked from the following command:

```
sudo apt-get update
```

Next, install Docker with the command:

```
sudo apt-get install docker.io
```

Check the installation (and version) by entering the following:

```
docker --version
```

If the docker version is displayed, then docker is installed successfully. Enable the docker service and check Status to make sure everything is working.

```
sudo systemctl enable docker
```

```
sudo systemctl status docker
```

6.2 Kubernetes

To install Kubernetes, we have used the instructions mentioned at the following URL:

<https://phoenixnap.com/kb/install-kubernetes-on-ubuntu#ftoc-heading-6>.

First of all, it is essential to ensure that the software is authentic. This is done by adding a signing key.

1. Enter the following to add a signing key:

```
sudo apt-add-repository "deb main" http://apt.kubernetes.io/kubernetes-xenial
```

```
curl -s https://packages.cloud.google.com/apt/doc/apt-key.gpg | sudo apt-key add
```

If you get an error that **curl** is not installed, install it with:

```
sudo apt-get install curl
```

2. Then repeat the previous command to install the signing keys. Repeat for each server node.

3. Kubernetes is not included in the default repositories. To add them, enter the following:

```
sudo apt-add-repository "deb main" http://apt.kubernetes.io/kubernetes-xenial
```

4. Installation of Kubernetes tools:

Kubeadm (Kubernetes Admin) is a tool that helps initialise a cluster. It fast-tracks setup by using community-sourced best practices. Kubelet is the work package, which runs on every node and starts containers. In addition, the tool gives you command-line access to clusters.

4.1. Install Kubernetes tools with the command:

```
sudo apt-get install kubeadm kubelet kubectl  
sudo apt-mark hold kubeadm kubelet kubectl
```

4.2. Verify the installation with:

```
kubeadm version
```

5. Kubernetes Deployment

5.1. Start by disabling the swap memory on each server:

```
sudo swapoff -a
```

5.2. Decide which server to set as the master node. Then enter the command:

```
sudo hostnamectl set-hostname master-node
```

5.3. Next, set a worker node hostname by entering the following on the worker server:

```
sudo hostnamectl set-hostname worker01
```

6. Kubernetes initialisation on Master Node

```
sudo kubeadm init --pod-network-cidr=10.244.0.0/16
```

Once this command finishes, it will display a kubeadm join message at the end. Make a note of the whole entry. This will be used to join the worker nodes to the cluster.

Next, enter the following to create a directory for the cluster:

```
kubernetes-master:~$ mkdir -p $HOME/.kube
```

```
kubernetes-master:~$ sudo cp -i /etc/kubernetes/admin.conf
```

```
$HOME/.kube/config
```

```
kubernetes-master:~$ sudo chown $(id -u):$(id -g) $HOME/.kube/config
```

7. Deploy Pod Network to Cluster

```
sudo kubectl apply -f
```

```
https://raw.githubusercontent.com/coreos/flannel/master/Documentation/kube-flannel.yml
```

Allow the process to complete. Verify that everything is running and communicating:

```
kubectl get pods --all-namespaces
```

<https://raw.githubusercontent.com/coreos/flannel/master/Documentation/kube-flannel.yml>

8. Join Worker Node to Cluster

As indicated in Step 7, you can enter the **kubeadm join** command on each worker node to connect it to the cluster.

Switch to the worker01 system and enter the command you noted from Step 7:

```
kubeadm join --discovery-token abcdef.1234567890abcdef --discovery-token-ca-cert-hash sha256:1234..cdef 1.2.3.4:6443
```

Switch to the master server and enter the following command to ensure the worker node is joined to the master node.

```
kubectl get nodes
```

6.3 Python

Since the solution from AI4EU is written in Python³⁵, we need to have a working Python Environment. The Python environment can be installed with the following commands:

```
sudo apt-get update
```

```
sudo apt-get install python3.8 python3-pip
```

To create a virtual environment, please run the following command:

```
python3 -m venv /path/to/new/virtual/environment
```

Run the following command to activate the environment:

```
source venv /path/new_env/bin/activate
```

³⁵ <https://www.python.org/downloads/release/python-370/>

7 Appendix 2

7.1 Related AI4EU Services

This section briefly outlines the AI4EU services that are candidates for alignment with I-ENERGY services. The actual alignment is provided in Table 4 and Table 5.

7.1.1 AI4EU-S1

Deep Autoencoders for Anomaly Detection

<https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/deep-autoencoders-anomaly-detection>

This resource presents a brief demo on applying Deep Autoencoders to create self-learning systems for anomaly detection. These algorithms present a huge potential in the generation of data-driven digital twins that can be applied to quality and process control, predictive maintenance and health monitoring. This demo applies a Deep Convolutional Autoencoder to a temporal series of data from an Anomaly Detection Benchmark.

7.1.2 AI4EU-S2

VisioRed

<https://www.ai4europe.eu/research/ai-catalog/visioired>

This component introduces a visualisation tool incorporating interpretations to display information derived from predictive maintenance models, trained on time-series data.

Dataset:<https://ti.arc.nasa.gov/tech/dash/groups/pcoe/prognostic-data-repository/#turbofan/>
Explanation techniques: LioNets, LIME, iPCA.

7.1.3 AI4EU-S3

Time prediction for flexible manufacturing

<https://www.ai4europe.eu/research/ai-catalog/time-prediction-flexible-manufacturing>

The code provides functions for training and evaluation of a stacked LSTM(Long short-term memory) model with spatial dropout. It predicts the duration of production per item for a given production plan. The products have different configurations (in this example, we have three different colours). In the pre-processing, the function can add padding to the sequence of products such that the LSTM trains well even if the starting time of the items is irregular. A simulation for the input data is included in the code. It serves as a basis for an uncertainty estimation (not covered in this code).

7.1.4 AI4EU-S4

Pump Failure Prediction

<https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/pump-failure-prediction>

The published PoC(Proof of Concept) integrates the first prediction models of pump failures. The extended solution will cover:

- The qualification of the existing quality control tools in terms of producing sufficient monitoring data for failure assessment.
- The qualification of customers' data is needed to describe the exploitation condition from the installation and during the exploitation process.
- The failure lifecycle assessment
- The Lifetime assessment process
- The root cause analysis of each failure step (installation, early exploitation at the first month, continuous pump exploitation)

The RUL; A comprehensive feedback mechanism to improve the manufacturing/quality control parameters.

7.1.5 AI4EU-S5

RL4Machine Tuning

<https://www.ai4europe.eu/research/ai-catalog/rl4machinetuning>

The RL4MachineTuning library proposes creating a tool embedding reinforcement learning (RL) applied to the tuning of industrial machine parameters to optimise the target application. The RL4MachineTuning library embeds an RL methodology, having the possibility to exploit user-specified reward/penalty functions, user-specified inputs, and user-specified outputs for the definition of the objective of the RL. These features make this library general and applicable to many applications, even outside the industrial context.

7.1.6 AI4EU-S6

Q-RUL

<https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/q-rul>

Q-RUL provides product lifetime estimation, fault identification and root cause analysis capabilities utilizing ensembles of state-of-the-art machine learning and deep learning techniques. Multiple RULestimation approaches are combined, using trained RNN and Transformer models. The first approach uses the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) algorithm, a special kind of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) with the capability to maintain temporal information to the network's nodes. Using LSTM, the RUL will be estimated upon run-to-failure data based on previous experience. The second approach uses Transformers, a special neural network based on the "attention" concept. Applying Transformers to the quality datasets will allow models to understand the important parts of quality measurements that affect the RUL of produced parts.

The model encodes the given sequences of quality measurements and decodes them to the RUL of produced parts. Time-series prediction performed with LSTM is the third approach to forming the RUL problem. Each quality measurement will be used to train a specific model to predict its future value. Quality measurement thresholds are used to assess the point where the predicted values violate the set thresholds (RUL). This type of RUL prediction can also be deployed along with produced part's installation in an edge device to collect data at run time and estimate the RUL online. The model also has auto-training capabilities if estimation error (e.g. RMS) is below a threshold. A meta-model is built to evaluate the performance of each approach, assigning weights in a way that the most accurate approaches are promoted. The result is a weighted average of all model outputs of each approach. To identify the early failure

of produced parts and become capable of timely identify what needs to be changed on the production parametrisation, classification models (CNN) will be trained upon quality measurements representing different failures forming a labelled training set. The classification models will be applied parallel to the RUL estimation ones in order to identify prominent failures. Another approach promoted is the training of separate RUL models, each one for each different failure mode, in order to provide separate RUL estimations per failure mode. This will be further extended with root cause analysis capabilities forming a Sequential Pattern Mining (SPM) problem with constraints. Solutions will be the sets of production parametrisations that lead to the identified failure modes so that the production engineers are in the place to know what exactly affected the RUL of produced parts negatively. The approach utilised is based on extensions to the Hirate-Yaman algorithm, often used for SPM problems with time constraints.

7.1.7 AI4EU-S7

HOPS

<https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/hops>

The proposed solution is a decision-support tool to define the proper stock level for end products and components. It will give purchase proposals in terms of quantity and delivery date per reference, considering the lead time for replenishment and the actual and on-arrival amount of stock.

7.1.8 AI4EU-S8

MPC-NODE

<https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/mpc-node>

SPDZ protocol describes a way to store user values and compute them when any node knows only self-value. Current protocol implementation consists of mpc-node part (contemporary service) and triple generator part - particular service node that creates Beaver triple for multiplication.

7.1.9 AI4EU-S9

Urban4Cast

<https://www.ai4eu.eu/resource/urban4cast>

According to the World Economic Forum, "mobility is a fundamental human need, and an essential enabler of prosperity, but the current mobility paradigm is not sustainable". The global mobility system is in the early stages of massive transformation worldwide, as novel technologies enable innovative related businesses. Moreover, policymakers seek out ways to foster mobility that becomes smarter, cleaner, and more inclusive. Cities worldwide have agreed on ambitious goals towards 2030 and regarding GHG emissions and carbon neutrality. Based on that ambitious roadmap, smart cities face challenges regarding active and shared mobility due to public transportation's low attractiveness and lack of real-time multimodal information for citizens. These struggles have highlighted the need to exploit all available city data for better understanding, learning, and predicting city's mobility behaviour to better urban planning. The proposed solution is an innovative data-driven and AI-based

approach that aims at helping cities to understand better the mobility patterns of their citizens for decision-making processes, named Urban Platform, which proposes data monitoring and leverages AI technology to analyse and forecast mobility behaviours on several data sources. It solves essential challenges about city management, such as monitoring and forecasting parking occupancy, using bicycles to optimise their location and traffic flow. Combining various data sources such as actual space usage, weather, population statistics for the quarters, and automated algorithms will provide more accurate predictions and be kept up to date. The demonstration will concern forecasts for historical and real-time data, and the models will be updated in real-time. The demonstration will also include estimates of different geographical areas, periods, and forecast windows. Finally, all data and forecasts obtained will be displayed on an open-source dashboard.

7.1.10 AI4EU-S10

VerifiAI

<https://www.ai4europe.eu/research/ai-catalog/verifai>

VERIFAI (Verifiable and Explainable Risk Forecasting Artificial Intelligence) aims to verify the reliability of a risk assessment tool performing a binary classification forecast. The tool tries to predict whether or not a given event will occur in a future time window of a given length.

7.1.11 AI4EU-S11

AI Industry Tutorial

<https://www.ai4europe.eu/research/ai-catalog/ai-industry-tutorial-04>

This is one of a series of tutorials that are part of the "AI in the Industry" course at the University of Bologna. Each tutorial tackles a simplified industrial problem and aims at showing how similar problems can be tackled using AI techniques, from Machine Learning to Combinatorial Optimisation (and later on their combination). This tutorial, in particular, addresses anomaly detection problems using neural models, in particular via density estimators (Real NVPs) and autoencoders. The tutorial also shows how to use binning to reduce subsample a high-frequency data series.

7.2 Use Cases

7.2.1 Use Case 1

This section briefly outlines the Partners’ feedback about the alignment between the I-ENERGY uses cases and the AI4EU services. The actual alignment is provided in Table 4 and Table 5.

Use Case-1 AI for enhanced network assets predictive maintenance, integrating off-grid data with condition-based monitoring

Pilot No. 1

Use Case Description

This use case refers to the detection and automatic analysis of faults in circuit breakers. This use case aims to form a detailed analysis supported by visualisations if possible and notify related authorities.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S1 (Deep Autoencoders for Anomaly Detection)

Partners’ Feedback

- 17) Yes
 - a) ICCS, CARTIF, COMS, DFKI
- 18) Partially Agreed
 - a) None
- 19) Not Sure
 - a) RWTH, ENG, FAEN
- 20) No
 - a) None

Related Service from AI4EU New website

AI4EU-S2 (VisioRed)

Partners’ Feedback

- 21) Yes
 - a) ICCS, COMS, DFKI
- 22) Partially Agreed
 - a) None
- 23) Not Sure
 - a) RWTH, ENG, FAEN
- 24) No
 - a) None

7.2.2 Use Case 2

Use Case-2 AI for network loads and demand forecasting towards efficient operational planning

Pilot No. 1

Use Case Description

This use case refers to the optimisation of the Network load using state of the art AI techniques. Internal services, such as forecasting, will rely on the accuracy of the predictions of the network load and will adapt accordingly in response to the traffic on the network.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S1 (Deep Autoencoders for Anomaly Detection)

Partners' Feedback

25) Yes

a) COMS, DFKI

26) Partially Agreed

a) ICCS

27) Not Sure

a) RWTH, ENG, FAEN

28) No

a) None

Related Service from AI4EU New website

AI4EU-S3 (Time prediction for flexible manufacturing)

Partners' Feedback

29) Yes

a) None

30) Partially Agreed

a) ICCS, DFKI

31) Not Sure

a) COMS, RWTH, ENG, FAEN

32) No

a) None

7.2.3 Use Case 3

Use Case-3 AI for energy demand prediction to optimise District Heating Network (DHN) operation.

Pilot No. 2

Use Case Description

This use case refers to optimising energy demand and supply in the DHN module, including various sub-services. For example, AI-based technologies could be used to estimate the emission and demand of the heating pipeline. The overall solution should also be cost-effective and environmentally friendly.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S4 (Pump Failure Prediction)

The published PoC integrates the first prediction models pump failures. The extended solution will cover:

- The qualification of the existing quality control tools in terms of producing sufficient monitoring data for failure assessment.
- The qualification of customers' data is needed to describe the exploitation condition from the installation and during the exploitation process.
- The failure lifecycle assessment
- The Lifetime assessment process
- The root cause analysis of each failure step (installation, early exploitation at the first month, continuous pump exploitation)
- The RUL; A comprehensive feedback mechanism to improve the manufacturing/quality control parameters.

Partners' Feedback

33) Yes

a) None

34) Partially Agreed

a) ICCS, CARTIF, DFKI

35) Not Sure

a) COMS, RWTH, ENG, FAEN

36) No

a) None

Related Service from AI4EU New website

AI4EU-S5 (RL4Machine Tuning)

Partners' Feedback

37) Yes

a) None

38) Partially Agreed

a) ICCS, COMS, DFKI

39) Not Sure

a) RWTH, ENG, FAEN

40) No

a) None

7.2.4 Use Case 4

Use Case-4 AI for energy-saving verification service, increasing the trust in energy performance contracts

Pilot No. 2

Use Case Description

This use case is related to implementing energy efficiency measures (ECMs) in different facilities, which will, in turn, reduce cost and unnecessary emissions. This will also help in accessing the condition of the components, e.g., if a component is making emissions that are above the acceptable level and cannot be controlled, then owners will be notified and forced to renovate the facility or building. The overall solution should also be cost-effective and environmentally friendly.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S6 (Q-RUL)

Partners' Feedback

41) Yes

a) None

42) Partially Agreed

a) None

43) Not Sure

a) DFKI, RWTH, ENG, FAEN

44) No

a) ICCS (Paid Service), CARTIF (Paid Service), COMS

7.2.5 Use Case 5

Use Case-5 AI for multi-energy systems decision support

Pilot No. 2

Use Case Description

This use case is related to the implementation of demand forecasting using AI technologies. The demand forecasting will help in reducing the cost and better management of energy consumption in the facility. It will also help in performing the analysis on the behaviour of users to predict the consumption. This use case focuses more on the user-end, and it impacts users directly with its reporting.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S7 (HOPS)

Partners' Feedback

45) Yes

a) None

46) Partially Agreed

a) ICCS, CARTIF, DFKI

47) Not Sure

a) COMS, RWTH, ENG, FAEN

48) No

a) None

Related Service from AI4EU New website

AI4EU-S5 (RL4Machine Tuning)

Partners' Feedback

49) Yes

a) None

50) Partially Agreed

a) ICCS, COMS, DFKI

51) Not Sure

a) RWTH, ENG, FAEN

52) No

a) None

7.2.6 Use Case 6

Use Case-6 Cross-functional AI-based predictive analytics to support integrated DSO's asset management and network operation

Pilot No. 2

Use Case Description

This use case aims to support Distributed systems Operator (DSO) via AI tools and technologies. We can support him by providing analytics charts and statistics about the assets which are managed by various underlying services. This will help DSO to manage his tasks which includes asset management and network optimisation effectively.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S1 (Deep Autoencoders for Anomaly Detection)

Partners' Feedback

53) Yes

- a) ICCS, CARTIF, COMS, DFKI

54) Partially Agreed

- a) RWTH

55) Not Sure

- a) ENG, FAEN

56) No

- a) None

Related Service from AI4EU New website

AI4EU-S2 (VisioRed)

Partners' Feedback

57) Yes

- a) ICCS, COMS, DFKI

58) Partially Agreed

- a) RWTH

59) Not Sure

- a) ENG, FAEN

60) No

- a) None

7.2.7 Use Case 7

Use Case-7 AI-based consumption and flexibility prediction for local community optimal aggregation and flexibility trading.

Pilot No. 3

Use Case Description

This use case aims to reduce the reverse power flow at the secondary substation. We shall also validate decentralised virtual power plant-based aggregation at the community level. It shall also provide local flexibility trading by utilizing P2P DLT and smart contract-based negotiation along with heterogenous customer types.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S1 (Deep Autoencoders for Anomaly Detection)

Partners' Feedback

61) Yes

a) None

62) Partially Agreed

a) CARTIF, ICCS, COMS, DFKI, RWTH

63) Not Sure

a) ENG, FAEN

64) No

a) None

Related Service from AI4EU New website

AI4EU-S11 (AI Industry Tutorial)

Partners' Feedback

65) Yes

a) None

66) Partially Agreed

a) ICCS, DFKI (Not a service but a tutorial), RWTH

67) Not Sure

a) ENG, FAEN

68) No

a) COMS

7.2.8 Use Case 8

Use Case-8 AI-based energy-driven and non-energy services.

Pilot No. 3

Use Case Description

This use case aims to target AI-based state of the art energy and non-energy services that can leverage the metering electricity consumption data for forecasting tasks.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S3 (Time prediction for flexible manufacturing)

Partners' Feedback

69) Yes

a) None

70) Partially Agreed

a) ICCS, COMS, DFKI

71) Not Sure

a) CARTIF, ENG, FAEN

72) No

a) RWTH

Related Service from AI4EU New website

AI4EU-S4 (Pump Failure Prediction)

Partners' Feedback

73) Yes

a) None

74) Partially Agreed

a) ICCS, COMS, DFKI

75) Not Sure

a) ENG, FAEN

76) No

a) RWTH

7.2.9 Use Case 9

Use Case-9 AI-based IoT-enabled PV module-level portfolio optimal predictive maintenance and PV-enhanced industrial plant optimal operation

Pilot No. 4

Use Case Description

This use case aims to perform optimisation of Industrial plant operations using state-of-the-art tools and technologies. It will also enable the improvement of data flow availability and predictive maintenance.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S1 (Deep Autoencoders for Anomaly Detection)

Partners' Feedback

77) Yes

a) None

78) Partially Agreed

a) CARTIF, ICCS, COMS, ENG

79) Not Sure

a) RWTH, FAEN

80) No

a) None

Related Service from AI4EU New website

AI4EU-S2 (VisioRed)

Partners' Feedback

81) Yes

a) ICCS, COMS, DFKI

82) Partially Agreed

a) ENG

83) Not Sure

a) RWTH, FAEN

84) No

a) None

7.2.10 Use Case 10

Use Case-10 AI in EV charging infrastructure

Pilot No. 5

Use Case Description

The aim of this use case is to improve user's experience at the charging stations by utilizing state-of-the-art AI tools and technologies. The developed module will identify the user's patterns and improve the load distribution at the stations. It will also help in saving energy which will make charging stations cost-effective.

No Related Service at AI4EU new and old platforms

7.2.11 Use Case 11

Use Case-11 AI for peer-to-peer renewable energy trading in virtual energy community

Pilot No. 6

Use Case Description

The aim of this use case is to encourage the community to use renewable energy and to educate users to perform energy trading using the Platform. The peer-to-peer trading platform will be developed using state-of-the-art AI tools and technologies.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S8 (MPC-NODE)

Partners' Feedback

85) Yes

a) None

86) Partially Agreed

a) None

87) Not Sure

a) DFKI, RWTH, ENG, FAEN

88) No

a) CARTIF, ICCS, COMS

Related Service from AI4EU New website

AI4EU-S2 (VisioRed)

Partners' Feedback

89) Yes

a) ICCS, DFKI

90) Partially Agreed

a) None

91) Not Sure

a) COMS, RWTH, ENG, FAEN

92) No

a) None

7.2.12 Use Case 12

Use Case-12 AI for Ambient Assisted living and personal safety/security at home

Pilot No. 7

Use Case Description

This use case aims to develop concepts, services and products using state-of-the-art AI tools and technologies. This will lead to better consumption and hence reducing cost.

No related service at AI4EU old and new platforms.

7.2.13 Use Case 13

Use Case-13 AI for energy efficiency investments

Pilot No. 8

Use Case Description

This use case aims for a Cost-effective assessment that ensures low-risk investments in energy efficiency and helps to categorize investment priorities. Secondly, it aims at providing holistic and reliable analysis that provides predictive maintenance warnings.

No related service at AI4EU old and new platforms.

7.2.14 Use Case 14

Use Case-14 AI for improved energy performance certificate's reliability

Pilot No. 9

Use Case Description

The aim of this use case is to use state-of-the-art AI tools and technologies to improve Energy Performance Certificate (EPC). The improvement is related to increasing reliability, making it cost-effective and EU legislation compliant.

No related service at AI4EU old and new platforms.

7.2.15 Use Case 15

Use Case-15 AI for predicting climate change impact in RES and energy demand at the regional level

Pilot No. 9

Use Case Description

This use case aims to provide Solar radiation forecasting of the Asturias region (Spain) and measure the impacts of climate change. It will also enable policymakers to generate new energy-based strategies.

Related Service from AI4EU

AI4EU-S9 (Urban4Cast)

Partners' Feedback

93) Yes

a) None

94) Partially Agreed

a) None

95) Not Sure

a) DFKI, RWTH, ENG, FAEN

96) No

a) CARTIF, ICCS, COMS

Related Service from AI4EU New website

AI4EU-S10 (VerifiAI)

Partners' Feedback

97) Yes

a) None

98) Partially Agreed

a) ICCS, COMS, DFKI

99) Not Sure

a) RWTH, ENG, FAEN

100) No

a) None